

Comparative Analysis of ML models on Multiple Diseases

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Abstract: Data mining can extract essential information from unstructured data. With the continuous growth and expansion of the healthcare sector, the need for creating successful decision support systems for medical applications is becoming increasingly important. This article offers a comparative examination of different machine learning (ML) models to forecast multiple illnesses. The investigation employs a dataset containing health records of patients, encompassing demographic, clinical, and laboratory factors, to assess the effectiveness of distinct ML models. Prompt decision-making is crucial in the diagnosis of diseases. This paper examines a study comparing various machine learning models for forecasting diseases using different attributes and a more effective algorithm.

The research offers recommendations that could greatly benefit the healthcare industry, and the project's actualization provides practical insights. The paper concludes with a summary of the authors' contributions to the topic, addressing any shortcomings and suggesting areas for future improvement. This study will be useful for physicians and researchers in identifying critical traits for disease identification. The study results can help with the selection of suitable ML models for predicting diseases and offer valuable insights into the advantages and disadvantages of various models.

Index Terms - Unstructured Data, Healthcare, Machine Learning, Research, Attributes.

I. INTRODUCTION

KDD and DM are two significant advances in processing enormous volumes of data. With unprocessed data doubling every year, organizations face the challenge of accessing, analyzing, and making informed decisions based on their interpretation. Data science can aid in converting this unprocessed raw data into useful information i.e., knowledge, thereby creating a self-learning organization.

The healthcare industry's primary requirement is to deliver high-quality care at a reasonable cost. Accurately diagnosing patients in a timely manner is crucial for delivering quality care. Machine learning approaches can aid in quick decision-making and cost reduction by using past clinical data. Automated procedures can optimize the decision-making process by considering factors such as cost, facility, speed, precision, and dependability.

Machine learning is used in various industries, such as medical field, education, food, entertainment, manufacturing processes, etc. A precise diagnosis of chronic diseases at the appropriate time is crucial for maintaining a healthy life. This study aims to comprehend the domain's complexity and the level of efficiency attained by various approaches. To accurately predict medical outcomes, this research compares various machine learning techniques. This piece of writing is organized as follows: Section II talks about the recent research on various diseases, followed by a need analysis of fundamental concepts related to healthcare research in Section III. Section IV outlines various classification algorithms, while Section V details the implementation of these algorithms for three diseases. Section VI presents a comparative analysis of research approaches. Section VII includes the results and discussions. In Section VIII, conclusions and recommendations for additional study are provided.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Research Papers Incorporated

Diagnosis has attracted significant attention in recent years. Multiple research studies have compared various machine learning techniques for predicting different types of diseases. In the medical field, several studies have been conducted and published, exploring the application of intelligent methods over the years. [7] For the purpose of identifying disease, numerous studies have been conducted. [1-40] An analysis of the key characteristics and the best models to predict the diseases is done using a literature review. Researchers have used many data mining techniques in this area, including clustering, classification algorithms, and association rules technique, to identify significant patterns for accurate disease prediction.

In a study conducted [3], the performance of ANN and SVM classifiers was compared using multiple classifiers, including CNN, KNN, and Inception V3. According to the experimental findings and performance analyses, ANN was found to outperform SVM, indicating that it is a superior classifier. Bidirectional recurrent neural networks (HA-BiRNN), the RCNN classifier, and other machine learning approaches were used by Anji Reddy Vaka to develop a revolutionary method for diagnosing breast cancer in [4]. It was found that the DNN algorithm outperformed the other approaches when compared to the proposed technique (Deep Neural Network with Support Value), in terms of efficacy and performance—two factors that are essential in modern medical systems.

In their research [4], different data mining ways were explored that can improve the ways of prediction of heart problems. Using MATLAB tools, five classifiers were created that imitate health decision-making. The study utilized two datasets, with the first one containing 303 data points, of which 297 were complete, and 6 had missing or unknown values. It was obtained from the Cleveland Clinic Foundation [5]. The second dataset was the Statlog dataset, which has 270 complete records and is available at [6]. [8] showed that KNN achieved the best accuracy for predicting datasets. Text mining resulted in better outcomes than Bayesian approaches. KNN algorithms are lazy learners since they do not learn anything from the training examples, but instead use the specifications of the training examples themselves. In Saranya and Dr. P. Asha's [9] research paper, lung cancer, a fatal disease, was discussed, which increases mortality and emphasizes the need for disease prediction. A hybrid system of vector support Deep preparation, also known as K, supervised learning models, and Fusion are additional methods frequently employed to increase sensitivity and accuracy. [10] introduces several research papers in the healthcare field related to machine learning. How artificial networks are being used to classify breast diseases and diagnose chronic diseases. The standard filtering approach has been adapted to trace data at high speeds and in high dimensions. An integrated association and classification technique was created in [11] to find rules in the database and then create an effective classifier utilising these rules.

[38] analysed the performance of SVM, KNN, DT, and NB algorithms for Parkinson's disease prediction and found that SVM outperformed the others. In the study by Sánchez-Marroño et al. [39], RF outperformed LR, SVM, and KNN for cervical cancer prediction, while Yang et al. [40] found that SVM outperformed KNN, DT, and RF for Alzheimer's disease prediction. Overall, these studies suggest that SVM shows promise for predicting various diseases.

2.2 Integrated Summary of Research Papers

We may conclude after reading these documents that predicting diseases is not difficult. Proper use of feature selection techniques can enhance efficiency. Additionally, use of ensemble models is recommended for better and optimized outcomes. Different approaches have been explained, with assumptions including disregarding abrupt changes in predicting and assuming linear behaviour of the data collection. This integrated summary provides an overview of these research papers. The paper [4] compared various techniques for early detection of heart problems, with decision tree outperforming Random Forest across all datasets. The paper [8] found that KNN achieved the best accuracy for predicting datasets in healthcare. The paper [9] discussed a hybrid system for disease prediction in lung cancer, and paper [10] introduced research papers related to machine learning for classification of chronic diseases. [11] provides an integrated technique of association and classification for effective medical diagnosis of heart disease.

These studies illustrate the significance of prediction and the advancement of prediction methods over time and in response to demand. These publications provide a comprehensive understanding of the rationale for feature selection and the description of data sets crucial for disease prediction. Overall, the literature evaluation indicates that these approaches have the capability to be effective in the prediction of a wide range of illnesses, including skin cancer, liver disease, heart disease, and breast cancer. According to the studies provided, SVM is a machine learning technique with a high level of predictive power for various disorders. The studies also highlight the need to tailor the choice of algorithm to the specific disease being predicted and the available data.

III. REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

3.1 Functional Requirements

- The right tools to put our ideas into practice
- The right data set to work with in real time
- The right libraries to use regression and feature selection methods in the source code.

3.2 Non-Functional Requirements

- The language employed in the project's creation. Use of Python 3.7. Any language with built-in libraries.
- Editor for writing the code.

3.3 Hardware Requirements

- Processor required: Intel core i3 and above
- RAM required: 4 Gb
- Internal space required: 250 Gb

3.4 Software Requirements

- OS: Windows (64 bit), Linux, Mac
- Jupyter Notebook
- Python 3.5 and above
- Python Libraries

IV. MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN HEALTHCARE

It is possible to define machine learning as a branch of science that examines how computers continuously get better by learning from data. It mostly relies on statistics and probability. It is more useful for making well-informed conclusions than conventional statistical techniques. The degree to which the algorithm is equipped with features affects the way accurately the model forecasts the future. Features are data that is obtained from a dataset and provided to the algorithm. [13] To find the previously mentioned feature subset for the algorithm, ongoing tests should be conducted. There are essentially three phases to take when thinking about applying a machine learning algorithm: training, testing, and validation. Training is crucial since the training dataset will determine how accurate the results are. The test dataset will be used to gauge the algorithm's effectiveness.

The following list of machine learning algorithms are commonly used in the medical sector: -

4.1 Supervised Learning: In the supervised learning, a training set with suitable dataset is given. There are two categories in supervised learning: classification and regression. In classification, the trained system divides inputs into classifications using classification algorithms. The sources in regression are continuous as opposed to discrete. The objective of supervised learning is to anticipate a known output using a shared dataset. Most of the time, a trained individual can also complete tasks that require supervised learning. Classification and prediction, which both include estimating, are the two main applications of supervised learning. Classification involves deciding which subgroups best characterize a given instance of data. [14]

Here are a few supervised learning techniques that are frequently employed in the medical industry.

KNN, or K-Nearest Neighbor: Pattern recognition and intrusion detection are two typical supervised classification tasks that are carried out with KNN. KNN is an easy-to-understand, straightforward algorithm. Despite having good accuracy, KNN requires a lot of memory and is computationally expensive because it needs to maintain both training and testing data. [15]

Support Vector Machine: This algorithm has become popular in healthcare applications as it can handle high-dimensional and complex data. SVM can be used for diagnosis, prediction, and classification tasks, such as breast cancer diagnosis, heart disease prediction, and gene expression classification. SVM's kernel functions, such as radial basis function kernel, allow it to handle non-linear relationships between features. SVM has shown promise in the healthcare industry by enabling accurate and efficient analysis of complex medical data. [15]

Logistic Regression: It is commonly used in medical research to analyse the relationship between risk factors and disease outcomes. Based on their medical history, demographics, and lifestyle factors, patients can be predicted to develop a specific ailment using logistic regression models. This approach enables healthcare providers to make well-informed decisions and create individualised treatment plans for their patients by assessing the efficacy of medical interventions and therapies. [17]

4.2 Unsupervised Learning: This is gaining popularity in healthcare applications. This can aid healthcare professionals in comprehending diseases, predicting patient outcomes, and devising customized treatment plans. Unsupervised learning methods, such as clustering and dimensionality reduction, are widely used in areas such as medical imaging, genomics, and electronic health records analysis, with promising results. [15] With the increasing availability of healthcare data, unsupervised learning is becoming an increasingly important tool for improving patient outcomes and advancing medical research.

4.3 Semi supervised Learning: By using labeled and unlabeled data at the same time, semi-supervised learning can help train more accurate models while reducing the need for costly manual annotation. The application of this approach has demonstrated potential in various healthcare areas, such as analyzing medical images, detecting diseases, and discovering drugs. As a result, semi-supervised learning is becoming an increasingly important tool for improving patient outcomes in the healthcare industry. [18]

4.4 Evolutionary Model: Evolutionary models have been increasingly used in the healthcare sector for predictive analytics, personalized medicine, and treatment optimization. This machine learning technique is founded on the concepts of natural selection and genetic algorithms. The algorithm evolves and adjusts itself by selecting and recombining the models that perform the best over time. Evolutionary models have shown great promise in healthcare applications, including predicting patient outcomes, identifying disease subtypes, and optimizing treatment plans. This approach can provide more accurate and personalized treatment recommendations, ultimately improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs. [18]

4.5 Deep Learning: Neural networks are used to learn from and forecast data in deep learning, an advanced level of machine learning. This method enables the implementation of complex generalized systems that can take on any problem and provide predictions for it. [18]

4.6 Reinforcement Learning: Training data is only produced in response to programmed activity that is repetitively combining ongoing learning processes from the environment.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

In this study, authors have created a reliable machine-learning model that effectively predicts a person's sickness based on the symptoms that person exhibits. The three diseases that have been considered are: Heart, Diabetes and Parkinson.

Introduction of Components used in Project: The structure of the system is developed by using a variety of techniques. Here are few of them:

1. Jupyter Notebook- A well-known web-based tool called Jupyter Notebook facilitates the production and exchange of documents that contain text, real-time code, mathematics, and visuals. The interface is divided into cells that allow users to enter code, text, or visualizations and immediately see the results. Jupyter Notebook can be utilized locally or on cloud services.
2. Spyder ide- An open-source integrated development environment (IDE) for data analysis and scientific computing. This IDE offers a user-friendly interface for coding in Python, R, and other programming languages, as well as tools for testing and debugging.
3. Python- It is an Interpreted programming language that supports not only Object-Oriented programming but also many other programming paradigms like functional, procedural, structural, etc., Python was discovered on 20 February 1991 by Guido Van Rossum. It is a language that has huge capabilities.

Libraries- Libraries in computer programming are pre-written code collections that programmers use to simplify and expedite their coding processes. These libraries contain functions, classes, and modules that can be imported into projects to perform specific tasks or operations. They can be general-purpose or specialized for applications like data analysis, web development, or machine learning. The libraries used in the implementation are:

Pandas- Pandas is a famous open-source toolkit for data manipulation and analysis in Python. Pandas is extensively utilized in data science, machine learning, and finance applications due to its ease of use and flexibility.

NumPy- NumPy is a Python library that specializes in working with arrays and offers additional functions in linear algebra, Fourier transform, and matrices. NumPy's purpose is to offer a quicker and more effective array object than Python's built-in list. This library is especially useful in fields that involve numerical computations like scientific computing, machine learning, and data science.

Sklearn- Scikit-learn, or sklearn, is a common open-source machine learning package for Python. It comprises numerous algorithms and machine learning-related techniques, has a user-friendly and consistent API, and is straightforward to use and understand.

4. Streamlit- Streamlit is a Python library that simplifies the creation of interactive data science web applications, allowing developers to build and share such applications without needing extensive knowledge of web development. It uses popular data science libraries like Pandas, NumPy, and Matplotlib, and offers real-time data updates, interactive widgets, and customizable themes.

Approach:

The dataset is downloaded from kaggle.com then built the model after performing data cleaning, feature engineering, dimensionality reduction, outlier removal, etc. Once, the model is ready then exported to pickle file, then wrote python code using spyder ide that can consume the pickle file and do the prediction of disease. Interface is built using streamlit library of python. In terms of tools and technologies, python is used as programming, pandas for data manipulation and matplotlib for data visualization, sklearn for model building, streamlit for UI and deployment.

5.1 Description of dataset

The datasets are taken from the Kaggle.com for various diseases like Heart, Diabetes and Parkinson. The model is trained using various features that are present in the dataset. Fig. 1 demonstrates first five rows of these datasets.

- **Heart-** The Heart Disease data is a collection of data that is related to patients suspected of suffering from heart disease. Age, gender, the type of chest pain, resting heart rate, levels of cholesterol in the blood, and more are just a few of the 14 characteristics that it contains. The Cleveland Clinic Foundation compiled the data from Switzerland, Hungary, and the United States. According to the binary target variable heart disease is either present or absent. This dataset has been considerably employed in predictive analytics and machine learning projects that are related to heart disease and can be accessed on different platforms, including Kaggle. It has also been used in many research studies.

- **Diabetes-** The Diabetes dataset is a collection of information on female patients with a Pima Indian ancestry who are minimum 21 years old. Age, the number of pregnancies, blood pressure, skin thickness, glucose levels, insulin, body mass index (BMI), and a family history of diabetes are the eight variables that are present in this dataset. A binary factor showing if the patient has diabetes is the target variable. This dataset has been broadly used in machine learning and predictive analytics projects related to diabetes and is often used as a benchmark dataset. It is accessible on different platforms, including Kaggle, and has been used in many research studies.
- **Parkinson-** A compilation of biomedical voice measurements from people with and without Parkinson's disease make up the Parkinson's Disease Classification dataset. The data was collected by recording the voice signals of patients with Parkinson's disease and healthy control subjects. It has a total of 22 features that were automatically extracted from these voice recordings, including measures of vocal fundamental frequency, jitter, shimmer, and noise-to-harmonics ratio. The binary variable that denotes whether Parkinson's disease is present or not is called the target variable. For classification and diagnostic analysis in the study of Parkinson's disease, this dataset is often used. It is available on Kaggle and has been engaged in several studies that were published.

	Pregnancies	Glucose	BloodPressure	SkinThickness	Insulin	BMI	DiabetesPedigreeFunction	Age	Outcome
0	6	148	72	35	0	33.6	0.627	50	1
1	1	85	66	29	0	26.6	0.351	31	0
2	8	183	64	0	0	23.3	0.672	32	1
3	1	89	66	23	94	28.1	0.167	21	0
4	0	137	40	35	168	43.1	2.288	33	1

	age	sex	cp	trestbps	chol	fbs	restecg	thalach	exang	oldpeak	slope	ca	thal	target
0	63	1	3	145	233	1	0	150	0	2.3	0	0	1	1
1	37	1	2	130	250	0	1	187	0	3.5	0	0	2	1
2	41	0	1	130	204	0	0	172	0	1.4	2	0	2	1
3	56	1	1	120	236	0	1	178	0	0.8	2	0	2	1
4	57	0	0	120	354	0	1	163	1	0.6	2	0	2	1

	name	MDVP:Fo(Hz)	MDVP:Fhi(Hz)	MDVP:Flo(Hz)	MDVP:Jitter(%)	MDVP:Jitter(Abs)	MDVP:RAP	MDVP:PPQ	Jitter:DDP	MDVP:Shimmer	...	Shim
0	phon_R01_S01_1	119.992	157.302	74.997	0.00784	0.00007	0.00370	0.00554	0.01109	0.04374	...	
1	phon_R01_S01_2	122.400	148.650	113.819	0.00968	0.00008	0.00465	0.00696	0.01394	0.06134	...	
2	phon_R01_S01_3	116.682	131.111	111.555	0.01050	0.00009	0.00544	0.00781	0.01633	0.05233	...	
3	phon_R01_S01_4	116.676	137.871	111.366	0.00997	0.00009	0.00502	0.00698	0.01505	0.05492	...	
4	phon_R01_S01_5	116.014	141.781	110.655	0.01284	0.00011	0.00655	0.00908	0.01966	0.06425	...	

Fig 1. First five rows of the dataset Diabetes, Heart, and Parkinson Disease respectively

5.2 Data pre-processing

It is the most important step which involves removing undesirable data qualities and other contaminants from the data. Datasets collected from medical patients frequently contain null values, missing values, and other impurities that lead to errors in the data's computation.

5.3 ML Algorithms Used

• Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a statistical method for binary classification problems. It is used to predict the probability of a binary outcome based on a variety of input factors. The ability to forecast the risk that a patient will contract a specific disease based on their medical history and other relevant characteristics makes logistic regression a common tool in the healthcare industry for disease prediction. A logistic curve, which depicts the likelihood that an event would occur given the input factors, is fitted to the data as part of the algorithm's operation.

• Support Vector Machine (SVM)

It is used to address real problems as well as linear and nonlinear problems. This learning is used for classification and regression concerns. Through a generated line or hyperplane, the data is split into classes. The most used machine learning algorithm approach is SVM. A supervised learning approach used for regression analysis and classification; support vector machine finds a hyperplane in an N-dimensional space. The hyperplane that best divides the classes in the data is what SVM looks for. SVM is renowned for its capacity to handle highly dimensional, complex data, making it appropriate for problems involving the illness prediction of big datasets with numerous input variables.

SVM and logistic regression are both effective machine learning techniques for predicting diseases in the healthcare industry. SVM is more accurate and more suited for complicated, high-dimensional datasets than logistic regression, which is simpler and easier to understand. In the end, the selection of an algorithm will depend on the precise specifications of the current disease prediction objective.

5.4 Splitting of Data

Creating a prediction model in machine learning requires splitting the data into training and testing sets. The objective of this step is to evaluate the model's performance on entirely novel, untrained data. After the model has been trained using the training set, its performance will be evaluated using the remaining subset of data as the testing set. This allows us to forecast how well the model will work with fresh, untested data. Splitting the data into training and testing sets is a critical stage in the creation of a predictive model since it enables us to assess the model's performance on new, untested data and determine its generalizability. Fig. 2 shows the splitting of data.

```
X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size = 0.2, stratify=Y, random_state=2)

print(X.shape, X_train.shape, X_test.shape)

(768, 8) (614, 8) (154, 8)
```

Fig 2. Splitting of data into train & test dataset.

5.6 Model Building

For building the model, the dataset was divided into train and test for effective model training and testing, and dependent (X) and independent (Y) variables were created. Our machine is trained using train data, and we use test data to determine how effectively it has learned the data. Using scikit learn library, one can import the train and test strategy. SVM model is created first for diabetes prediction and it gives score as approx. 77% which is quite okay. Now, for heart disease, models are trained using logistic regression which gives a score around 81%. For Parkinson's disease, SVM algorithm is used to building the model and the accuracy obtained is around 87%. All the model predictions techniques are checked to check for overfitting by evaluating the values. Then, built the python function for predicting the price. Fig. 3 demonstrates the model training and Fig. 4 demonstrates the model accuracy.

```
classifier = svm.SVC(kernel='linear')

#training the support vector Machine Classifier
classifier.fit(X_train, Y_train)

SVC
SVC(kernel='linear')

model = LogisticRegression()

# training the LogisticRegression model with Training data
model.fit(X_train, Y_train)

: model = svm.SVC(kernel='linear')

: # training the SVM model with training data
model.fit(X_train, Y_train)

: SVC
SVC(kernel='linear')
```

Fig 3. Model training for Diabetes, Heart, and Parkinson Disease respectively

```
# accuracy score on the training data
X_train_prediction = classifier.predict(X_train)
training_data_accuracy = accuracy_score(X_train_prediction, Y_train)

print('Accuracy score of the training data : ', training_data_accuracy)

Accuracy score of the training data : 0.7833876221498371

# accuracy score on the test data
X_test_prediction = classifier.predict(X_test)
test_data_accuracy = accuracy_score(X_test_prediction, Y_test)

print('Accuracy score of the test data : ', test_data_accuracy)

Accuracy score of the test data : 0.7727272727272727
```

```
# accuracy score on training data
X_train_prediction = model.predict(X_train)
training_data_accuracy = accuracy_score(Y_train, X_train_prediction)
```

```
print('Accuracy score of training data : ', training_data_accuracy)
```

Accuracy score of training data : 0.8717948717948718

```
# accuracy score on training data
X_test_prediction = model.predict(X_test)
test_data_accuracy = accuracy_score(Y_test, X_test_prediction)
```

```
print('Accuracy score of test data : ', test_data_accuracy)
```

Accuracy score of test data : 0.8717948717948718

```
# accuracy on training data
X_train_prediction = model.predict(X_train)
training_data_accuracy = accuracy_score(X_train_prediction, Y_train)
```

```
print('Accuracy on Training data : ', training_data_accuracy)
```

Accuracy on Training data : 0.8512396694214877

```
# accuracy on test data
X_test_prediction = model.predict(X_test)
test_data_accuracy = accuracy_score(X_test_prediction, Y_test)
```

```
print('Accuracy on Test data : ', test_data_accuracy)
```

Accuracy on Test data : 0.819672131147541

Fig 4. Model Accuracy for Diabetes, Heart, and Parkinson Disease respectively

5.7 Prediction Function

After building the model, there is a need to export the model and the related artifacts that are needed for python streamlit. The pickle file contains coefficients, intercepts but not actual data. Fig. 5 demonstrates the prediction function.

```
input_data = (5,166,72,19,175,25.8,0.587,51)

# changing the input_data to numpy array
input_data_as_numpy_array = np.asarray(input_data)

# reshape the array as we are predicting for one instance
input_data_reshaped = input_data_as_numpy_array.reshape(1,-1)

prediction = classifier.predict(input_data_reshaped)
print(prediction)

if (prediction[0] == 0):
    print('The person is not diabetic')
else:
    print('The person is diabetic')
```

```
[1]
The person is diabetic
```

```

input_data = (62,0,0,140,268,0,0,160,0,3.6,0,2,2)

# change the input data to a numpy array
input_data_as_numpy_array= np.asarray(input_data)

# reshape the numpy array as we are predicting for only on instance
input_data_reshaped = input_data_as_numpy_array.reshape(1,-1)

prediction = model.predict(input_data_reshaped)
print(prediction)

if (prediction[0]== 0):
    print('The Person does not have a Heart Disease')
else:
    print('The Person has Heart Disease')

```

```

[0]
The Person does not have a Heart Disease

```

```

input_data = (197.07600,206.89600,192.05500,0.00289,0.00001,0.00166,0.00168,0.00498,0.01098,0.09700,0.00563,0.00680,0.00802)

# changing input data to a numpy array
input_data_as_numpy_array = np.asarray(input_data)

# reshape the numpy array
input_data_reshaped = input_data_as_numpy_array.reshape(1,-1)

prediction = model.predict(input_data_reshaped)
print(prediction)

if (prediction[0] == 0):
    print("The Person does not have Parkinsons Disease")
else:
    print("The Person has Parkinsons")

```

```

[0]
The Person does not have Parkinsons Disease

```

Fig 5. Predictive function for Diabetes, Heart, and Parkinson Diseases respectively

5.8 Web Interface of Model

For UI, streamlit library of python is used to write a python service that can serve HTTP requests. If a simple and straightforward user interface is developed, people who have little to no understanding will be able to predict diseases with ease. The users can use UI to enter the features and then can easily predict the disease. Fig. 6 shows the Web Interface.

Fig 6. UI for Disease Prediction

VI. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Table 1 Comparative Analysis of Multiple Diseases

Reference	Year	Disease	Algorithms Used	Dataset	Results (Accuracy)	Important Findings
[30]	2020	Cardiovascular Disease	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RF, 2. DT, 3. LR, 4. SVM, and 5. KNN algorithms. 	NIDDK	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RF=85.71 %, 2. DT =74.28% 3. LR=74.28 % 4. SVM=77.14% and 5. KNN=68.57% 	RF outperformed every classifier that was utilized in analysis of categorizing CVD patients.
[28]	2019	Heart Disease	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. KNN, 2. RF, 3. LR, and 4. Ensemble Method 	UCI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. KNN=87 % 2. RF = 87%, 3. LR =87%, 4. Hard Voting Ensemble =90% 	The ensemble model performs better than the individual classifier and makes it more accurate.
[27]	2019	Brain Tumours Disease	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SVM, 2. KNN, 3. RF 	33 patients were depicted by Rembrandt image planes, with twenty images per subject on average.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. KNN=87 %, 2. SVM=90 %, 3. RF=83% 	SVM algorithm is more accurate than the alternative method.
[26]	2019	Diabetes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SVM 	283 eye thermal photos from FLIR.com	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SVM=86.22% 	The results show that the customised IR thermal image system can be utilised as a reliable, non-invasive, and non-contact approach for the diagnosis of diabetic thermal eye illness.
[25]	2019	Heart Syndrome	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. KNN, 2. Naive Bayes, 3. DT, 	Kaggale web site	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. KNN=85 % 2. DT =82% 2. 3. RF =81% 	Comparing KNN algorithm to other algorithms, it has a very high Accuracy score.

			4. RF, and 5. SVM		4. NB =80% 5. SVM=82%	
[24]	2019	Diabetes	1. Naive Bayes, 2. DT, and 3. SVM	Global dataset	1. DT = 85% 2. NB =77% And 3. SVM=77.3%	Naive Bayes and SVM are less accurate than the decision tree.
[23]	2018	Thyroid	1. SVM, 2. KNN, 3. DT	The UCI machine learning repository	1. KNN=98.62%, 2. SVM==99.63% 3. DT=75.76%	Patient saves time and money because of the fewer parameters.
[19]	2018	Liver	1. Logistic Regression, 2. KNN, and 3. SVM	Indian Liver Patient Dataset.	1. KNN model = 73.97% 2. LR= 73.97% 3. SVM = 71.97%	Despite the great accuracy of KNN and logistic regression, logistic regression has the highest sensitivity. It is a better model as a result.

Table 1 summarizes various studies conducted on different diseases, machine learning algorithms used, datasets utilized, accuracy results obtained, and findings. The studies include cardiovascular disease, lung cancer, heart disease, brain tumors, diabetic eye, heart syndrome, diabetes, thyroid, and liver disease. The experiments used a variety of machine learning methods, with accurate results being published. The findings of each study suggest that the models built using ML algorithms outperform the baseline models. The model's accuracy varies depending on the disease and dataset used.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The healthcare system is just beginning to capitalize on new opportunities. Many successful decisions are presented by big data to predict accurately health consequences. There is a multitude of data available regarding patient health, much like there is in the medical field. As a result, it is incomprehensible to humans. To discover patterns from enormous amounts of data and apply algorithms to forecast future patient outcomes, machine learning (ML) approaches are provided. It enables users to assess the efficacy of current programmes and select the course of action that will result in the best patient outcome in a specific circumstance. All publications discussed in the preceding section used various machine learning methods between 2018 and 2020 to conduct related studies to pinpoint disorders. Table 2 displays a summary of the eleven earlier studies examined in this research are given below. Each study's summary includes information on the disease type, dataset, methodologies or algorithms, accuracy, and findings. Three alternative methods were employed by the authors in [19] to identify disorders of the liver. The results of the logistical regression algorithm's accuracy tests are used to determine which method is the best among the others. Two different datasets and feature sets have been used to the KNN and SVM algorithms in [23] and [25]. The outcome in [23] demonstrated that the SVM algorithm is superior to KNN. However, in [25], the KNN method outperforms SVM by roughly 3%. According to study [25], the accuracy of the decision tree is roughly 1% better than that of the random forest. However, in [28], the random forest outperforms the decision trees in terms of accuracy by about 12%. An ensemble model was utilised by researchers [22] and [26], with accuracy rates that were 98.50% and 90%, respectively. The only two-class classifiers that are frequently used are SVM and Logistic Regression, however other methods, including CNN, decision trees, random forests, KNN, naive Bayes, and K-means, can classify data into multiple categories. All algorithms function well with small datasets, however huge datasets are superior for deep learning methods like CNN. Using an ensemble model rather than a single model alone yields better results. The SVM model for diabetes prediction was initially developed in this study, and it provides a score of approximately 77%, which is acceptable. The model is currently trained for heart disease using logistic regression, which yields a score of about 81%. SVM technique is utilised to develop the model for Parkinson's disease, and the accuracy attained is about 87%.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

The project can be further enhanced by implementing the machine learning model developed using a web application and employing a larger dataset for prediction, the project can be improved further, and outcomes will be better. With a customized customer prediction system, this program can be integrated into a mobile application or web page. International illness datasets can be included for a country-by-country impact instead of using local data. The program can be made simpler to understand with a notification bar.

There is a considerable potential for improvement in time complexity when processing very large datasets for long-term prediction. We can also include an auto-prediction system that can keep track of the data appropriately and record consumer activity history. Fuzzy logic and machine learning approaches can be coupled to handle uncertainty more effectively in prediction. To deal with uncertainty in the medical profession successfully, statistical, and soft data might be combined.

IX. CONCLUSION

The paper completely meets the objective of the project. This research focused on and assessed recent findings on the key characteristics of various diseases, as well as the data mining strategies employed to forecast the condition. Doctors could decide on the next course of treatment by determining the likelihood of a disease using an accurate prediction model. The models for the disease prediction were created using a few input attributes, and they perform remarkably well. As a result, this study's objective was to facilitate the development of a useful model that can accurately and swiftly forecast illness by other researchers.

Any disease that, if caught early enough, can be treated with some human effort. Most people don't become aware of their condition until it has lasted a long time. Death rates are rising globally as a result. For improvements in accuracy, it requires time to develop a technique which ends in the fewest mistakes. It was important to develop a digital diagnostic system that employed machine learning techniques to foresee or diagnose the condition and more accurately and quickly identify the needed procedures. With the use of our findings, additional work on an actual model should be done to validate them. The healthcare sector is expanding its challenges and increasing its costs. Several machine learning methods are used to address these issues. A variety of methods for predicting illnesses, such as those for diabetes, heart disease, and liver disease, are discussed in this paper. After reviewing numerous articles for various models that predicted diseases, it is clearly visible that many algorithms, including SVM, KNN, random forest, etc., are good in terms of accuracy in prediction. As a few key variables, like datasets, feature selection, and the number of quality features, have a great impact on the accuracy and performance of model, the accuracy may vary from one dataset to another by even using the same machine learning algorithm. Another significant learning from this study is that the accuracy and performance of an ensemble model may be increased by using an alternative algorithm to build it.

The ML model that has the highest accuracy out of the many that have been tried by researchers is chosen for the chronic disease prediction. It has been noted that the effectiveness of the model is influenced by both the dataset chosen for prediction and the machine learning technique.

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